

Multimedia skills for effective performance in digital media lab in university libraries

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Abstract: The digital media lab in the university libraries provides students and faculty members access to a workstation or maker space equipped with professional free and open-source multimedia software and tools for graphic design, audio and video editing, web and app development, game design, animation, and programming. This paper explores various skills that will enable librarians and multimedia developers to effectively operate in a digital media lab. The paper tries to look at the required digital media skills based on different job responsibilities of a multimedia developer.

Keywords: Multimedia, Multimedia Skills, Digital Media, Digital Media Lab, Trend in University Libraries

Introduction:

University libraries traditionally create access to information resources and supply diverse academic needs of students and faculty. Beyond that, libraries perform other supporting roles that involve somewhat information technology skills. Librarians now take part in some roles that were traditionally performed by computer scientists or information technologists to keep the library afloat with 21st century best practices and emerging technologies. With the influx of emerging technologies in the education system generally and university library in particular, such that multimedia resources keep surging in demand for students learning enrichment, innovation and development; creation of digital media lab in the university library becomes indispensable.

Digital Media Lab and Services:

A digital media lab or student multimedia studio is a place generally equipped with a variety of tools and resources for people to collaborate learn and share knowledge. Also as a place that can give people exposure to something they may not otherwise have access to, the digital media lab gives students the tools to create PowerPoint, web, video/audio presentations and e-Portfolios, as well as scan and edit documents and photographs, create graphics and animation and receive one-on-one instructional support from peer mentors or professional staff (Kent State University, n. d.). This space offers students resources to work on a variety of multimedia projects, whether for a class or personal use.

Digital media lab or students multimedia studio offers a variety of software tools and equipment for users to engage in several multimedia activities such as video editing, audio recording, game design, animation, 3D modeling, and other multimedia related works. Kennedy, the manager of library maker spaces in Kent State University states that the student multimedia studio also offers a 3D printing service, capture station that takes old media, like VHS tapes,

records, and audio cassette tapes, and digitizes them onto the computer (Kent State University, n. d.).

Fisher (2016) states that digital media lab (DML) has evolved as the logical next stage in the firmly established digital evolution to enable patrons to make creative content in innovative spaces chock full of computer hardware and software alongside audio, digitizing, graphic design, music, photography, video, web publishing, and other production equipment and resources.

According to Fisher (2018), patrons can use a digital media lab in four meaningful ways, such as: curating their personal and community history such as digitizing and preserving photos, slides, and videotapes; creating original digital content such as videos, music recordings, and graphic/web designs; collaborating on projects through library-sponsored opportunities and informal partnerships; and sharing finished work with the world for others to discover and use.

Operating a digital media lab in the university library will enable patrons to understand and handle the complex technology architecture and also eliminates the digital divide by making technological tools available and creating easy access to them.

Using a digital media lab depends on the personal goals of the patrons. According to Fisher (2016), digital media lab will engage patrons in a wide range of activities and projects which include: transferring VHS tape to DVD; recording an instructional video segment for a local business; drawing Manga using a tablet and illustration software; laying down beats, recording original vocals, then uploading the song to Soundcloud; creating an original model to make with a 3D printer' scanning pictures and creating a slideshow to celebrate a personal milestone; repairing a damaged photo, then surprising a loved one with a high-quality print of the restored version; recording a podcast' programming a robot to complete a task; designing an invitation; editing a video and sharing it on YouTube; earning a filmmaking badge as part of a scouting program; photographing products for an online store promotion; meeting with a client to discuss revamping a website; rehearsing with a band for an upcoming musical performance; printing a large poster to promote an event and collaborating on a school project.

Overview of Multimedia:

Multimedia technology has become prevalent in the educational system and has been widely employed in teaching and learning across nations. Multimedia has also gained wider access into the business world especially in the area of branding and marketing. In virtual, all areas of human endeavor, multimedia is an indispensable tool to reckon with. However, multimedia could be defined as a combination of various mass media such as print, audio, and video. Anyim (2018) defines multimedia as a combination of different digital resources to mechanize the methods, procedures, and routines used to present information or knowledge. It also involves a combination of text, graphic art, sound, animation, and video elements. On the other hand, multimedia combines various learning tools using computer-based hardware and software packages to present information. Different terms can be used to describe multimedia such as Audio-visual, hypermedia, courseware, Intelligent Tutoring Systems, and multimedia (Anyim, 2019).

Multimedia are various media resources that include text, graphics or images, audio, or video used to make teaching and learning easy and interesting (Nwangwu and Obi, 2014). Multimedia is utilized through the aid of a computer (National Open University of Nigeria, 2006). Most of the definitions include the application of multiple forms of media such as texts, graphics, animations, video, and sound in the learning process (Anyim, 2020). Multimedia is used as learning resources, means of communication used across topics. Multimedia brings together

different resources such as text, graphics, animation, pictures, video, and sound for the presentation of concise, precise information. Multimedia are basically computer-aided information resources that preserve, store, and transmit. Multimedia combines both computer hardware and software that allow the integrated media to function and enrich students' understanding (Surjono, 2015).

Multimedia helps in simplifying contents and makes it easy for users to understand messages clearly; helps to facilitate the design of applicable knowledge; enhances students' comprehension of a concept at their own pace; makes knowledge more flexible than text or speech; presents teachers and learners with unique learning resources that can be used in a wide variety of ways to simulate various forms of learning; ensures that abstract principles learned by users through the text are presented in form of animation or a video; enhances deeper comprehension and also enables users to form a mental image of abstract verbal realities (Bent and brink, 2013). From the foregoing, multimedia technologies and their application in teaching and learning obviously present university lecturers a golden opportunity to tap from the potentials of multimedia technology in preparing, updating, or teaching so as to improve insight and the quality of the course or lessons. In order to operate a student multimedia studio in the university library, multimedia librarians should possess adequate competencies in multimedia creation and editing such as animation creation, audio recording, graphic/image design, and editing. This involves inserting objects or text, deleting unwanted information, modifying graphics or images, audio clips, video clips, or animated objects in order to make them more meaningful and useful as to meet the objective for which such application is meant (Anyim, 2019).

Multimedia Components:

- i. **Text:** Text is an important component of multimedia. It is used to create meaning or pass human knowledge. Text is used to represent specific knowledge or information. It consists of letters or characters or words used to describe or classify information contained in multimedia. Encyclopedia (2016) defines texts as characters that are used to create words, sentences, and paragraphs useful at providing basic information. Ali (2019) opines that text creation or word processing is crucial in preparing multimedia instructional materials.
Knowledge of word processing software makes it easier for multimedia developers to mix words with video, image/graphic, or animation when developing multimedia. The beauty of multimedia depends on the skill to integrate two or more media to present knowledge or information and also to edit or update contents.
- ii. **Audio:** Audio is an essential component of multimedia. Audio is referred to as a voice or sound that signifies an action (Nwangwu and Obi, 2014). From a teaching and learning perspective, audio integrated multimedia makes learning effective. Audio makes teaching and learning so interesting and gives students a pleasant experience (Uzuegbu et al., 2013).
- iii. **Graphic/Image:** Graphic/image gives multimedia a peculiar meaning. Graphics/images include all forms of drawings, images/ photographs, and other non-textual contents represented in a digital format (Nwangwu and Obi, 2014). Graphic/images are digital representations of non-text information such as drawings, charts, or photographs which are found resourceful in communication and education (Encyclopaedia, 2016). The effectiveness of multimedia in the

graphic presentation is the ability to use images as a message in a clearer way (Reddi and Mishra, 2003).

- iv. **Video:** A video is also an effective tool for demonstrating practical and abstract concepts. The video component of multimedia combines text, audio, static or motion pictures to pass the information which makes learning more engaging; makes the presentation of the event, situation, and phenomenon more possible and realistic and simplifies knowledge with clarity (Madu and Nwangwu, 2014).
- v. **Animation:** The animation is an indispensable component of multimedia. It is presented as a motionless image or quietly moving image or object in sequential order on the computer or projector. Animation has the potential of presenting real objects through simulations (Nwangwu and Obi, 2014). Animation enhances one's experience and allows user to widen their knowledge boundaries. The virtual effect given to animation helps in providing objective information, experiential account of an event; it helps to take users to the scene and allows them to experience an event for themselves. Animation creation programs include Microsoft Office PowerPoint, Adobe Flash, Cinema 4 D, and so on (Encyclopedia, 2016).

Basic Multimedia Skills for Librarians:

Skill means required to perform a task in an expected way. Skill is also an accumulated knowledge that enables one to perform a job accurately and effectively. Nwangwu and Obi (2014) defined skill as the effective application of knowledge in such a way that tasks are executed effectively and efficiently. The skill requires specialized knowledge, technical know-how, or exceptional ability to perform certain tasks well. Multimedia skill is defined as the ability to effectively and efficiently design, develop, integrate, and implement multimedia technologies for effective instructional delivery (Anyim, 2019). Multimedia skills for librarians are grouped into four basic components which include: text, graphic/images, audio, video, and animation (Anyim, 2019). Basic multimedia skills are discussed under the following headings:

- i. **Textual Creation Skills:** This involves creating, naming and saving a document; formatting document; inserting image; creating hyperlink; adding virtual appeal/cell shading; insert header or footer; creating page orientation; creating Custom Margin; text alignment in tables (Anyim, 2019).
- ii. **Audio and Video Creation and Editing Skills:** This involves recording live audio/video; converting text into speech with the aid of "text to speech" tool; expunging or removal of unwanted parts of an audio/ video clip; exporting/importing audio files across audio editing platform; remixing or mixing different audio files; apply noise reduction effect to audio or sound files; fading in and out audio in a video; adding audio on youtube; changing the background music in video (Anyim, 2019).
- iii. **Graphic/image Creation and Editing Skills:** This involves creating images for motion pictures and animation; designing themed presentation; cropping images to maximize copy space; resizing and skew images to a particular dimension; designing visual assets for social media; matching colors within the design to enhance beauty; converting graphic image file formats to other formats; merging objects together using the blend tool; pair contrasting fonts and add transparent icons (Anyim, 2019).

- iv. **Animation Creation Skills:** This involves developing a custom show in PowerPoint; converting PowerPoint presentation to video; designing instructional picture slide show in flash; exporting image/movie files for use in others platform; creating a storyboard for animation video; write a stellar video script; importing multimedia elements into adobe flash stage; organizing multimedia elements in layers and designing motion tween animation (Anyim, 2019).

Skills and Responsibilities for Multimedia Developers in the Digital Media Lab:

Several skills and responsibilities are sines qua non for effective job performance in the digital media lab. Digital media lab which is also referred to as multimedia studio in this study requires the services of multimedia developers or specialists. These groups of professionals are expected to possess certain skills to carry out some responsibilities which Zippia, the career expert (n. d) identifies as follows:

Graphic Design:

- i. Interact with colleagues and outside vendors to ensure high-quality illustrations and graphic design were maintained.
- ii. Handle projects on graphic design.
- iii. Consult with visual/graphic designers to conduct usability testing prior to development to lower overall development costs.
- iv. Produce a variety of communications materials including graphic design, photography and video.

Adobe Illustrator:

- i. Design logo and business cards for Drive Ideas in Adobe Illustrator.
- ii. Create images and animation for a corporate informational video using Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Flash, and Adobe Illustrator.
- iii. Design and teach curriculum centered on student needs for courses in Google Sketch-Up, Adobe Illustrator and Adobe Photoshop.

Html:

- i. Contribute to web-based projects using HTML and web-development applications.
- ii. Coordinate efforts of programmers and designers by evaluating the possibilities and limitations of Dynamic HTML features in Microsoft Internet Explorer 5.
- iii. Develop company websites and campaign content with XHTML, ASP.NET and CSS technologies with Adobe CS/CC software.
- iv. Develop marketing campaign complete with website and video advertisements using HTML embedded video and Flash video.

Instructional Design:

- i. Manage internal project staff of programmers and instructional designers.
- ii. Contribute to project structure and instructional design.

- iii. Design and copy-edit full-color wall calendar promoting the Instructional Design Services division
- iv. Collaborate with Instructional Designers on storyboards, animations, and content for web-based training.

Captivate:

- i. Develop and integrate post-exams utilizing Adobe Captivate.
- ii. Develop banners in flash to effectively captivate viewers to the site and inform potential clients about the company's web products.
- iii. Develop complex branching, remediation, and navigation in the courseware using advanced actions in Adobe Captivate.
- iv. Provide an enhanced learning experience through the design and development of interactive games using Adobe Flash and Captivate.

E-learning:

- i. Work on eLearning games, training courses, graphics and animations using various design and animation software.
- ii. Produce eLearning training presentations and user guides.
- iii. Design advertising materials.

Video Creation:

- i. Establish an animation studio, direct, and edit video productions.
- ii. Manage audio/video productions, design Flash games, animations, and other applications for online courses and online marketing campaigns.
- iii. Manage Digital Audio/Video production, quality control, and final evaluation of all digital media production.
- iv. Produce interactive web banners, animated presentations as well as video production and editing.

Photoshop:

- i. Create training development software, such as Lectora Inspire version 12.1, Adobe CreativeSuite including Photoshop, InDesign.
- ii. Create printed material and optimize photographic images using Photoshop, InDesign, and Illustrator.
- iii. Create original graphics, custom user interfaces in Photoshop and Illustrator.
- iv. Perform basic graphic editing using Photoshop and Paintshop.

Interactive Multimedia:

- i. Supervise technical personnel in procedures and implementations of interactive multimedia instruction design and development.
- ii. Use instructional design documents and state-of-the-art tools to develop interactive multimedia instruction products.

- iii. Create interactive multimedia instructional content outlines, flowcharts, and storyboards that address written, visual, and audio requirements.
- iv. Develop interactive multimedia instruction and courseware

User Interface:

- i. Collaborate with design teams in planning, designing and implementing application user interfaces.
- ii. Design user interface and implement websites for several projects.
- iii. Develop training, interactive applications and create user interface (UI) design for a certified Adobe training studio.
- iv. Develop organized parts and graphics database, to include reusable templates and components for user interface.

Scorm:

- i. Develop graphic assets that conformed to SCORM standards which allowed artists to quickly adapt graphics to make updates.
- ii. Ensure SCORM conformance and Section 508 compliance using the VA WBT templates.
- iii. Provide project management and support for implementing SCORM-compliant modules. Rice:
- iv. Programme SCORM integration and validated courseware performance.

JavaScript:

- i. Programme HTML and JavaScript web pages for client projects, corporate website, and company intranet.
- ii. Utilize JavaScript to create custom interactivity for the AS3 applications in web browsers.
- iii. Integrate and maintain websites using HTML, CSS and JavaScript.
- iv. Author CBT and EPST applications using ToolBook and HTML/JavaScript.

Company Website:

- i. Design, develop, manage and give strategic direction for the (company) website.
- ii. Create photo-realistic 3D kitchens in 3DS max for use on (company) websites.
- iii. Serve as a web designer for company websites.
- iv. Design and produce corporate identity, and maintain company website.

CSS:

- i. Complete cross-browser CSS code for online training modules, and websites.
- ii. Implement complex Flash websites and applications Maintained and debugged CSS for client sites, including cross-browser and cross-platform consistency and compatibility
- iii. Design iPhone Application, Design, Concept and Coding in CSS, XCode and iPhone Simulator.

- iv. Develop CSS styles for Themes and rebranding.

Training Programs:

- i. Develop computer-based training programs for the ExxonMobil Corporation.
- ii. Collaborate with organizational executives in the development and execution of customized on-site training and off-site training programs.
- iii. Facilitate training programs, develop guides and materials for trainers and participants
- iv. Maintain attendance records and participant evaluations for all training programs.

PowerPoint:

- i. Produce three instructor-led PowerPoint presentations, instructor guides, and student workbooks.
- ii. Advance knowledge of LMS authoring packages (Articulate Studio 09, Storyline 2 and PowerPoint).
- iii. Integrate complex concepts for award-winning scientific exhibits and PowerPoint presentations for clients.
- iv. Develop a how-to video incorporating interactive features, audio, and graphics to educate University staff and students on editing PowerPoint presentations.

Multimedia:

- i. Form a sole proprietorship to develop multimedia applications used for presentations, promotional material, consumer products, and other projects.
- ii. Conduct market analysis and testing of digital asset management systems and multimedia software.
- iii. Consult with various University departments on potential multimedia projects, including interactive sites and portals.

Online:

- i. Create original graphics and interactive animations in Adobe Flash for online lessons in college-level courses.
- ii. Create participant workbooks and facilitator scripts designed for digital delivery to complement online training modules.
- iii. Create user interface/experience for all online, desktop, and email-based applications.

SMEs:

- i. Work directly with SMEs and ISDs to establish academic learning objectives
- ii. Interface directly with SMEs and client stakeholders to rapidly develop and edit handheld-compatible training material to meet very aggressive timelines.
- iii. Work with primary stakeholders and SMEs.
- iv. Develop effective working relationships with SMEs to efficiently collect content information and feedback.

Subject Matter Experts:

- i. Work with client subject matter experts to develop advanced learning content
- ii. Collaborate with subject matter experts on how best to express their training with the illustrations.
- iii. Work with subject matter experts to resolve issues with visual content.
- iv. Work with Subject Matter Experts (SMEs) to developed Storyboard.

Dreamweaver:

- i. Use Dreamweaver, Cold Fusion Studio or HomeSite to create code templates.
- ii. Utilize Dreamweaver and Flash for design.
- iii. Publish and edited articles using Dreamweaver.
- iv. Design, develop and manage institutional and community websites using Dreamweaver MX and Adobe Photoshop.

XML:

- i. Modify login page, introduction video, and developed XML and SWF files for the world map.
- ii. Streamline the deployment process of eLearning programs utilizing Flash and XML.
- iii. Expand system diversity allowing localization of user interface through XML injection.
- iv. Develop dynamic data-driven, turn-key learning modules that are 100% SCORM & 508 compliant using AJAX and XML.

Product Photography:

- i. Design products, brochures, trade show banners and take product photography.
- ii. Create slideshow videos of the current season's lifestyle and product photography.
- iii. Design storyboards, product photography shelf sets, animated gifs, video reels, internal presentations, and corporate headshots.

Learning Management System:

- i. Apply state-of-the-art learning technologies (learning management systems, content management systems) to customer requirements.
- ii. Develop online interactive training modules compatible with the proprietary learning management systems.
- iii. Develop and maintain a custom Learning Management System.
- iv. Integrate training applications with customer's in-house Learning Management System (LMS) utilizing LDAP.

Adobe Premiere:

- i. Learn and use Adobe premiere pro, light room, and after effects at an advanced level within initial 6-month period.

- ii. Import and edit footage for internal and consumer facing videos using Adobe Premiere and Final Cut Pro.
- iii. Assist in editing of sales seminar videos, using Adobe Premiere Pro.
- iv. Use Adobe Premiere to create and edit audiovisual E-marketing blast utilized for advertising objectives.

Camtasia:

- i. Create computer-based training modules/videos using Camtasia and Flash.
- ii. Design e-training demonstration modules using Camtasia Studio 7 software.
- iii. Record and edit Subject Matter Expert teleconference meeting in Camtasia.
- iv. Produce training courses using various applications including MS Word, MadCap Flare and Camtasia.

Action script:

- i. Create a functioning online board game using an Action script which can be used to present training modules to employees.
- ii. Optimize Action script code for good processor speeds on both high and low-end machines for a variety of different browsers.
- iii. Create, develop and maintain e-learning applications using Macromedia Flash, ActionScript 2.0, 3.0 and PHP/MySQL.
- iv. Create various text effects and ActionScript for Adobe Flash CS6 with SWISHmax.

Jquery:

- i. Design and Build a responsive web application using CSS3, media queries, jQuery, JSON, building web pages for clients,
- ii. Develop applications to report specific data using JQuery, AJAX, CSS and XML/JSON.
- iii. Implement JQuery for Client-Side Sorting and Validations; and secondary validations from the Business Layer of 3-tier application.
- iv. Improve the efficiency of co-workers through the use of a task manager written in jQuery and ColdFusion.

PHP:

- i. Implement and maintain a PHP based Bug Tracker for internal company use.
- ii. Implement company s FOXTM PHP-based message board utility.
- iii. Maintain the Wabash valley visions and voices website which is built with PHP as the back end.

DVD:

- i. Authorize a DVD menu with Intro, Chapter Selection, and Bonus Features; also designed user interface for the menu.
- ii. Produce infomercials/commercials for distribution on DVD, CD, television broadcast and Internet.

- iii. Coordinate with the Media Department in preparing video for DVD, CD-Rom and Web Streaming.
- iv. Produce complete virtual tour video and authorize to DVD for office lobby display.

CD-ROM:

- i. Develop and design an interactive CD-ROM based video library using Director.
- ii. Perform a bevy of tasks related to the development of rich media computer-based training products for web and CD-ROM delivery.
- iii. Manage and Develop large-scale custom database-driven web and CD-Rom based solutions for both web and non-web-based clients.
- iv. Create children's educational software titles, CD-ROM electronic catalogs, and computer-based training courses.

CBT:

- i. Develop CBT solutions for publishers to make large amounts of PDF data accessible on e-books.
- ii. Create computer-based training (CBT) modules focused on the implementation of category selling.
- iii. Provide technical support for CBT and tracking of students.

Web Services:

- i. Support community businesses with custom graphic and web services.
- ii. Manage web content and web services.

SQL:

- i. Design and/or implement databases for web sites and other applications (Access, SQL Server).
- ii. Create maintain and managed RDB (Relational Database) under the MySQL and SQL platforms.
- iii. Create triggers and stored procedures in SQL Server.
- iv. Develop automated customer follow-up email response system with PHPMyAdmin and MySQL.

Internet:

- i. Update and maintain user accounts, system configurations, daily backups, and frame-relay internet configurations and connections.
- ii. Develop a wide range of instructional training material delivered on CD-ROM, over the LAN, or on the Internet.
- iii. Design Internet and Intranet
- iv. Coordinate and produce in-house and outside client video, CD-ROM, and internet productions for the digital media production facility.

Website:

- i. Design and develop websites on education and digital media streaming.
- ii. Propose, create, and enables two corporate web sites and two e-commerce sites.
- iii. Develop fully interactive websites for a variety of purposes.
- iv. Design email postcards and Flash websites.

ASP:

- i. Maintain and develop large interactive web applications using ASP.
- ii. Code and implement various aspects of universal AS3 video player for all of WDPRO sites.
- iii. Involve in all aspects of digital media development, from concept to completed project
- iv. Design and programme an intranet database (SQL Server) application using both Authorware and Active Server Pages (ASP).

Authorware:

- i. Develop an online ordering system for disk drive manufacturer using Authorware
- ii. Design and programme an Authorware CD application for the U.S.
- iii. Create interactive electrical, hydraulic, and pneumatic drawings using Macromedia Authorware.
- iv. Create secured briefings using Photoshop, PowerPoint, and Authorware.

Training Materials:

- i. Create a variety of training materials for companies.
- ii. Collaborate with SAP configuration team and process owners to ensure technical accuracy and instructional effectiveness for classroom training materials.
- iii. Conduct thorough interviews with multiple subject matter experts to source curriculum content ensuring relevancy and accuracy of training materials.
- iv. Create and publish training materials for instructor-led classes for use by administrators using Xerox custom applications and PowerPoint

Final Cut Pro:

- i. Edit video for websites and CD-ROMs using Final Cut Pro.
- ii. Use Final Cut Pro X, Sony Vegas Pro, and DVD mastering software to create and edit video content.
- iii. Edit video projects for DVD and Web distribution using Final Cut Pro, After Effects and Flash Video.
- iv. Administer lesson in Final Cut Pro, Avid, and After Effects.

Fireworks:

- i. Utilize Adobe Flash, Adobe Fireworks, Microsoft Office, and voice recording software (VLC).

- ii. Design logos for use on business stationery and web pages using Fireworks.
- iii. Develop an interactive Request for Proposal solution for the sales group utilizing Adobe Dreamweaver, Adobe Fireworks, and Adobe Acrobat.
- iv. Follow storyboards to produce animated Flash courses Produced graphics in Fireworks and Photoshop for use in animated courses.

Interactive Content:

Develop animation and interactive contents.

Final Product:

- i. Assist with the interpretation of regulations/doctrinal publication/policies, procedures, and validation of the final product to ensure adherence to established guidelines.
- ii. Design detailed and literal graphic representations of the final products.
- iii. Consolidate assets and final product master files for archiving purposes.
- iv. Interface with Programmers, Instructional Designers and Subject Matter Experts to hone content for a final product.

Windows:

- i. Review feature specifications and research Windows source code to create and improve reference documentation.
- ii. Assemble desktop personal computers; install Windows operating systems and other software.
- iii. Train the Department of Education's staff on digital video content creation and Website streaming using Windows Media technology.
- iv. Utilize the ASP.NET development framework and Visual Studio to build Windows mobile applications and dynamic web sites.

Digital Video:

- i. Draft specification and strategy for one terabyte system of digital video storage.
- ii. Manage broadcast-quality digital video facility with workstations.
- iii. Create video assets using a non-linear digital video editing system.

Conclusion:

The creation of digital media labs in university libraries is rapidly increasing with high demand for skilled workers including librarians, multimedia developers, and other media experts. Competition for those jobs will be stiff, and individuals in the field must be dedicated to keeping their skills as current as possible. As discussed earlier, multimedia covers different digital media combined to present information in a unique way. It includes interactive presentations used in business environments; interactive websites on the Internet; video games, audio and video clips, motion and still pictures; animation; graphics and etc. Multimedia is developed and delivered using computer hardware and software. Certain skills are required to allow users to navigate through the

media tools to create or develop multimedia. Individuals who combine artistic ability with digital proficiency design and create multimedia products. Librarians are encouraged to develop themselves to become multimedia developers and media specialists to be able to manage and operate the digital media lab in their university libraries. Students multimedia studio or digital media lab will help students practice what they have virtualized, become creators of their own intellectual property, create innovations, and develop technological tendencies and initiatives that will enable students to create multimedia products and on the other hands, push the rank of the university up to the ladder of great reputation. Exploring the various skills used in the multimedia studio has presented librarians and multimedia developers the opportunity to know what skills are expected of them to possess in order to utilize digital media lab in the university library in the most effective way.

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